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ANNOTATION

This article deals with the analysis of lexical syntactic stylistic devices and expressive means in stylistics. It is determined due to the fact that the investigation of lexico-syntactical stylistic devices in the English language plays the great role in studying English as a second language.

KEY WORDS: - climax(gradation), anticlimax, antithesis, litotes, simile, periphrasis, represented speech.

Stylistics, a branch of applied linguistics, is the study and interpretation of texts of all types and/or spoken language in regard to their linguistic and tonal style, where style is the particular variety of language used by different individuals and/or in different situations or settings.

What is the purpose of stylistics? Stylistics examines the creativity in the use of language. It enhances the way we think about language and its uses. Thus the stylistic process, examining the creativity of language use, develops our understanding of literature.

The climax in a short story is the turning point where the protagonist confronts the main conflict, creating the most intense moment. For example, in "The Lottery," the climax occurs when Tessie discovery that she had "won" the lottery and was to be stoned to death.

What is an anticlimax?

An anticlimax is a rhetorical device that functions as an abrupt let-down or tonal shift at the end of a narrative build up. The term can best be described through examples. Think of a romance novel, where two characters have a will-they-won't-they relationship building throughout the story. At the end of the novel, when the two characters are on top of a ferris wheel gazing over their hometown, they don't kiss and, instead, go home and never confess their love for each other. That's an anticlimax.

Antithesis is a literary device that positions opposite ideas parallel to each other. Think heroes and villains, hot and cold, bitter and sweet. Antithesis enhances your writing by illuminating differences and making your point more persuasive.

What is antithesis?

Antithesis (pronounced an-TITH-uh-sis) deals in opposites. The Merriam-Webster definition of antithesis is “the direct opposite,” and in Greek the meaning is “setting opposite.” As a tool for writing, antithesis creates a juxtaposition of qualities using a parallel grammatical structure. In other words, it’s setting opposites next to each other using the same terms or structure. This creates a stark contrast that highlights dramatic qualities and creates a rhythm that’s interesting to the reader.

What is the definition of litotes in writing?

The definition of litotes sounds more complicated than its actual use: They are phrases that express an affirmative by denying its opposite, usually through understatement.

Some examples of litotes that you might find in everyday speech are:

You can’t say I didn’t warn you.

Meaning you did, in fact, warn them.

That wasn’t half bad.

Meaning it was actually quite good.

What is a simile?

A simile (SIM-uh-lee) is a type of figurative language that describes something by comparing it to something else with the words like or as.

Even if you don’t know the definition like the back of your hand, you’ve probably seen plenty of similes. For example:

I know that definition like the back of my hand.

Those two are as different as night and day.

In linguistics and literature, *periphrasis* (/pəˈrɪfrəˌsɪs/)[1] is the use of a larger number of words, with an implicit comparison to the possibility of using fewer. The comparison may be within a language or between languages. For example, "more happy" is periphrastic in comparison to "happier," and English "I will eat" is periphrastic in comparison to Spanish "comeré."

Represented speech. is used to convey the actual utterances of characters more adequately and emotionally. It conveys the actual words or thoughts of a character not directly, but within the author's speech, retaining the peculiarities of the speaker's manner of expression

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